

Figure Z9

Figure Z9: Original cell type annotation and marker gene expression for a single-cell mouse skeletal muscle study. (A) Single-cell clustering of 10,368 cells in GSE150065. The UMAP plot is coloured by clusters. **(B)** Cell-type marker gene expression. **(C)** Same UMAP plot coloured by original cell type labels provided by the authors. **(D)** Further split of tenocytes into two states. MTJ, myotendinous junction specialization; NMJ, neuromuscular junction. Other abbreviations used in this figure appear in the Methods.